

TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND ITS USAGE OF IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE CONVERSATION

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Annotation: Speaking is the expression of one's thoughts in order to solve communication problems. This is the activity of one person, although it is included in communication and is unthinkable outside of it because communication is always interacting with other people. The goal of education in secondary school should be considered not language, which is appropriate for philological education in a special university, and not speech as a "way of forming and formulating thoughts".

Keywords: methodological literature, formation of communicative competence, linguistic environment, intercultural communication.

Аннотации: Говорение есть выражение своих мыслей в целях решения задач общения. Это деятельность одного человека, хотя она включена в общение и немислима вне его, ибо общение — это всегда взаимодействие с другими людьми. Целью обучения в средней школе следует считать не язык, что уместно при филологическом образовании в специальном ВУЗе, и не речь как «способ формирования и формулирования мысли».

Ключевые слова: методическая литература, формирование коммуникативной компетенции, языковая среда, межкультурная коммуникация.

Uzbekistan has established itself as a reliable and solvent partner, where almost unprecedented conditions have been created for attracting foreign capital. This requires the growth of qualified and competent foreign language specialists. Therefore, in recent years, the number of people learning English has increased dramatically. Currently, it is impossible to do without knowledge of a foreign language. The age threshold for learning English dropped to preschool age. This situation creates the need of society for qualified teachers since until now the methodology was focused primarily on schoolchildren. And when teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of children. The main purpose of a foreign language as a subject area of school education is seen in the mastery of students the ability to communicate in a foreign language. We are talking about the formation of communicative competence, i.e. the ability and willingness to carry out both direct communication (speaking, listening comprehension) and indirect communication (reading with an understanding of foreign language texts,

writing). The formation of communicative competence is the main and leading goal of training¹. Speaking is the expression of one's thoughts in order to solve communication problems. This is the activity of one person, although it is included in communication and is unthinkable outside of it because communication is always interacting with other people. The goal of education in secondary school should be considered not language, which is appropriate for philological education in a special university, and not speech as a "way of forming and formulating thoughts"², and not even just speech activity - speaking, reading, listening, or writing, but the indicated types of speech acts as a means of communication.

One of the most controversial aspects of the problem of teaching foreign languages is the verification and accounting of knowledge, skills and abilities, the methodology of their organization and implementation³.

Control has not yet become a "powerful lever" for improving academic performance and a source of help to establish the true state of knowledge and skills in a given subject. Recently, an important attitude in the areas of teaching foreign languages has become the emergence of a draft educational standard in a foreign language, developed under the leadership of M.A. Beam and academician A.A. Mirolyubov. The interim standard defines the basic, minimum sufficient level of training, as well as the goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages. Only a meaningful and properly organized control correlated with them can contribute to the achievement of these goals and objectives⁴.

The research material is presented in the following sequence:

In the Introduction, a justification of the relevance of the work is given, the goal, objectives, object, and subject of research are determined. The first chapter reveals the scientific foundations for the implementation of the development of speaking skills and the criteria for its automation at different stages of training, examines the types and forms of work in teaching speaking, as well as the requirements for its implementation. The second chapter is devoted to the specifics of using sample dialogues and other types of speech activities to

¹ Мирульд Р.П., Максимова И.Р. Современные концептуальные принципы коммуникативного обучения иностранным языкам // Иностранные языки в школе. – Москва, 2000. - №4. – С. 9-15

² Климентенко А.Д. Экспериментальное обучение английскому языку детей с шести лет в школе // Иностранные языки в школе. – Москва, 1978. - № 2. - С.37-47

³ Гальскова Н.Д., Никитенко З.Н. Организация учебного процесса по иностранным языкам в начальной школе // Иностранные языки в школе.- Москва, 1994 - №1 - С.8-16

⁴ Бим И.Л., Биболетова М.З. Возможные формы и содержание курсов обучения иностранным языкам в начальной школе // Иностранные языки в школе. Москва, 1991.- № 2 - С.23-24

develop the skills and abilities of students. A number of useful tips are also given for the development of speech-thinking activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. The conclusion is a summary of the entire study, contains some recommendations on the use of exercises aimed at developing communication skills. The bibliography provides a list of references to sources used.

The principle of speech direction. The speech orientation of the educational process lies not so much in the pursuit of a practical speech goal, but in the fact that the path to this goal is the very practical use of the language. Practical speech orientation is not only a goal but also a unity. Speech orientation presupposes a lack of exercise, i.e. degree, a measure of their similarity to speech. All of them should be exercises not in speaking, but in speaking, when the speaker has a specific task and when he carries out speech influence on the interlocutor. The principle of speech orientation also involves the use of communicatively valuable speech material. The use of each phrase should be justified by considerations of communicative value for the intended sphere of communication (situation) and for this category of students. The speech character of the lesson also plays an important role here.

The principle of functionality. Any speech unit performs any speech functions in the process of communication. Often, after a course of study, students, knowing the words and grammatical forms, cannot use all this in speaking, because no hyphenation occurs (when pre-filling words and forms apart from the speech functions they perform, the word or form is not associated with the speech task). Functionality determines, first of all, the selection and organization of material adequate to the communication process. Approaching the needs of communication is possible only when taking into account speech means and organizing the material not around conversational topics and grammatical phenomena, but around situations and speech tasks. The unity of the lexical, grammatical, and phonetic aspects of speaking is also necessary.

The principle of novelty. The communication process is characterized by a constant change of the topic of conversation, circumstances, tasks, etc. The novelty provides the flexibility of speech skills, without which their transfer is impossible, as well as the development of speech skills, in particular its dynamism (methodically unprepared speech), the ability to paraphrase (the quality of productivity), the combination mechanism, the initiative of the utterance, the tempo of speech, and especially the strategy and tactics of the speaker. This requires constant variation in speech situations.

Situationism is one of the main principles of teaching speaking, the principle of situationally. Situationism as a principle in general terms means that all teaching of speaking occurs on the basis and with the help of situations⁵. In addition, the definition of the concept of "situation" in the communicative method differs significantly from the known definitions. Any teacher knows the facts when, having received an assignment: "Speak in a situation "At the checkout," the student is silent, although it is well known that the situation always has a stimulating force. If this situation ("At the cash desk") does not evoke a statement, obviously, this is not a situation. But why are these situations used in teaching? The reason for this is the popular definition of a situation as a combination of circumstances ("At the cash desk", "At the cinema", "At recess", etc.). So, by naming the circumstances, an attempt is made to set the situation from the outside. But in this case, it is not accepted by the student. And how can you relate to the words "At the cash desk"? When people communicate at the box office (in the cinema, at the station), different situations may arise, because the situation arises only when there is a relationship between the communicating people, and depends primarily on them, and not on the place where it occurs. This is due to the fact that the situation is reflected in the minds of the speakers. When a person speaks, he, of course, refers his words to objects of reality, but at the moment of speaking, he most often relies not on them, but on mental images. This means that there is an internal visualization, by the fact that the speech situation is understood as something ideal, it does not break away from reality at all. This only emphasizes the methodologically important feature of the situation, the absence of a direct attachment of speech units to the circumstances present at the moment. How the situation "turns out" to be reflected in consciousness. The fact is that the situation is not a local segment of reality, but a "segment" of activity, a form in which the interaction of communicants is carried out. Therefore, the situation is characterized by the main features of the activity: meaningfulness, heuristic, hierarchy, and a certain structure. It is also important to note that the interaction of the communicators arises when solving a problem. From a methodological point of view, this is very important, since it forces you to organize situations as an activity consisting of solving communication problems. The core of the situation reflected in the consciousness is the relationship of the communicators⁶.

⁵ Богородская В.Н. "The World of Britain" – новый учебник для 10-11 классов школ с углубленным изучением английского языка // Иностранные языки в школе. – Москва, 2000. - № 3. – С. 15-20

⁶ Программа по английскому языку для начальных школ. – Москва: «Просвещение», 2005. - 128 с.

If one person is indignant at someone's actions, and the other justifies him or agrees with it, then "indignation is justification" or "indignation-consent" is the situation. Of course, this is only its basis, on which a lot is layered, including external circumstances. But only the presence of this foundation creates a true situation that will serve as the basis for teaching speaking. The language teaching methodology should provide training for all types of monologue speech. The purpose of teaching monologue speech is the formation of speech monologic skills:

- 1) retell the text, make a description, a message on a given topic, compose a story;
- 2) to logically consistently open a given topic;
- 3) substantiate the correctness of their judgments, including in their speech elements of reasoning, argumentation. All these skills are developed in the process of performing preparatory and speech exercises.

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